

Stratified Hypothesis Testing of Mean Duration of Response in Randomized Clinical Trials

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Abstract

Duration of Response (DoR) is an emerging endpoint of clinical interest in randomized clinical trials (RCTs) by simultaneously considering the maintenance of response along with the achievement of the response in a patient. The summary measure of the single DoR endpoint is typically summarized among responders, i.e., not reflecting the intent-to-treat (ITT) population. Combining DoR with achievement of response as a composite endpoint warrants further consideration for summary metric and statistical comparison in the ITT population, particularly within clinical trials using stratified randomization. By utilizing a mixture distribution framework, we propose a stratified hypothesis test to compare two arms in RCTs using the difference in Expected DoR (EDoR). In this paper, simulations are conducted to evaluate the performance of this methodology, and an example is shown to demonstrate the application of the method.

Key Words: duration of response; accelerated failure time; stratified design; stratification factor

1. Introduction

A patient's achievement of response defined by a clinical response evaluation criterion for the investigated disease is often used as an endpoint in a randomized clinical trial (RCT), aggregated as the proportion of total patients achieving the response, and compared between arms using difference in proportions, odds ratio, relative risk, etc., to evaluate the treatment effect. Duration of Response (DoR) is another important measure of treatment effect, which can be used to evaluate the treatment's ability to provide sustained response, typically analyzed within patients who achieved response. However, comparison of DoR within responding patients may be biased in favor of the experimental treatment, where response rates are presumed to be higher under the alternative hypothesis. To comply with the intent-to-treat principle and adequately compare the experimental treatment to the control, a statistical test to evaluate DoR should consider incorporating all randomized subjects, i.e., the intent-to-treat (ITT) population, rather than among those who responded.

To address such concern, Ellis et al. (2008) utilized a mixture distribution to estimate the Expected DoR (EDoR) based on a parametric accelerated failure time model and then performed a ratio test of EDoRs from two arms in an RCT. However, the ratio test is not able to accommodate stratification factors, typically expected for a clinical trial utilizing stratified randomization. Another approach by Huang and Tian (2022) uses a restricted mean DoR (RMDoR), which could be considered a nonparametric analog to EDoR. We focus on parametric development on EDoR in this paper. Based on the mixture distribution framework of Ellis et al. (2008), we propose a new test statistic that combines the achievement of response and DoR in patients to test the difference of EDoRs from two arms in an RCT within the ITT population. More importantly, accommodation to a stratified

design becomes straightforward when one applies our proposed difference test statistics, i.e., a stratified test based on difference statistics utilizing stratification factors. In the simulation study, we compare the stratified testing method with unstratified method, which shows the necessity of considering stratification factors in a stratified design. Finally, we conduct an analysis using data from patients with acute myeloid leukemia as an illustrative example.

2. Proposed Method

2.1 Ellis' Method

Ellis et al. (2008) calculated (1) the proportion of patients who respond to treatment, and (2) the duration of response among those who respond to treatment in both the experimental and control groups, then calculated the expected duration of response (EDoR) based on these two estimates. Consequently, hypothesis testing can be employed to assess the treatment effect between groups.

Consider a randomized trial to compare the efficacy of a new drug E, with a control drug C, among two groups of patients with sample size N_E and N_C , respectively. Let p_E and p_C represent the true response rates, and M_E and M_C represent the true average duration of response for the responding patients. We define $R = \frac{\text{EDoR}_E}{\text{EDoR}_C} = \frac{p_E M_E}{p_C M_C}$ as the EDoR ratio. To obtain the EDoR estimate, we take the logarithm and replace p_E, p_C, M_E , and M_C with their corresponding MLE estimates:

$$\log(\hat{R}) = \log(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_E) - \log(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_C)$$

Assuming that the response rate and DoR between two treatments are independent, $\widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\widehat{\text{EDoR}})]$ can be expressed as

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\widehat{\text{EDoR}})] = \frac{1}{\hat{p}^2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}) + \frac{1}{\hat{M}^2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{M})$$

we can calculate the variance of above as $\widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\hat{R})]$:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\hat{R})] &= \widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_E)] + \widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_C)] \\ &= \frac{1}{\hat{p}_E^2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}_E) + \frac{1}{\hat{M}_E^2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{M}_E) + \frac{1}{\hat{p}_C^2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}_C) + \frac{1}{\hat{M}_C^2} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{M}_C) \end{aligned}$$

So, the hypothesis that the EDoRs of the new drug E and the control drug C are equal can be tested as follows:

$$H_0: R = \frac{\text{EDoR}_E}{\text{EDoR}_C} = 1 \text{ vs. } H_1: R = \frac{\text{EDoR}_E}{\text{EDoR}_C} \neq 1$$

Using Z as the test statistic

$$Z = \frac{\log(\hat{R})}{\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}[\log(\hat{R})]}}$$

which follows a standard normal distribution under the null distribution.

2.2 Hypothesis Testing

To compare the treatment effects between the experimental and control groups, we need to estimate EDoR for all patients in both groups. Since the response rates and DoR to treatment may vary among patients in different stratification factors in a stratified design, this section will explain how to perform a stratified hypothesis test.

For simplicity, we assume all patients come from the same strata (e.g. homogeneity). Instead of using EDoR ratio, we develop a null hypothesis based on the difference in EDoR ($H_0: \text{EDoR}_E - \text{EDoR}_C = 0$). The derivation of the test statistic for this is as follows:

Define $D = \text{EDoR}_E - \text{EDoR}_C = p_E M_E - p_C M_C$, and substitute the MLE of p_E, p_C, M_E , and M_C to obtain the estimate of D :

$$\hat{D} = \widehat{\text{EDoR}}_E - \widehat{\text{EDoR}}_C = \hat{p}_E \hat{M}_E - \hat{p}_C \hat{M}_C$$

Using the same assumption as Ellis et al. (2008), we assume that the response rate and DoR are independent, $\text{Var}(\widehat{\text{EDoR}})$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}) &= \text{Var}(\hat{p}\hat{M}) = E(\hat{p}^2\hat{M}^2) - E(\hat{p}\hat{M})^2 = E(\hat{p}^2)E(\hat{M}^2) - E(\hat{p})^2E(\hat{M})^2 \\ &= (\text{Var}(\hat{p}) + E(\hat{p})^2)(\text{Var}(\hat{M}) + E(\hat{M})^2) - E(\hat{p})^2E(\hat{M})^2 \end{aligned}$$

we can calculate the variance $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{D})$ as the following,

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{D}) &= \widehat{\text{Var}}(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_E) + \widehat{\text{Var}}(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_C) \\ &= \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}_E \hat{M}_E) + \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}_C \hat{M}_C) \end{aligned}$$

So, the hypothesis that the EDoRs of the new drug E and the control drug C are equal can be tested as follows:

$$H_0: D = 0 \text{ vs. } H_1: D \neq 0$$

Using Z as the test statistic

$$\begin{aligned} Z &= \frac{\hat{D}}{\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{D})}} \\ &= \frac{\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_E - \widehat{\text{EDoR}}_C}{\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_E) + \widehat{\text{Var}}(\widehat{\text{EDoR}}_C)}} \sim N(0,1) \end{aligned}$$

Next, we extend the difference statistic to the setting where we collect patients from different strata. To account for this heterogeneity, we can obtain the overall EDoR for all patients by calculating the EDoR for each strata's patients and performing a weighted average. Similarly, the difference in EDoR between the two arms could be utilized to determine if there is a significant difference in treatment. The derivation of the test statistic for this is as follows:

Consider a randomized trial comparing the efficacy of a new drug E and a control drug C in two groups of patients with N_E and N_C . For the i -th strata ($i = 1, \dots, m$), let p_{Ei} and p_{Ci} represent the true response rates in each stratum, and M_{Ei} and M_{Ci} represent the true average duration of response for patients with a response. Let n_{Ei}, n_{Ci} be the number of people in the experimental and control group of the i -th strata respectively. Let D' be the difference in EDoR between study groups under heterogeneity setting:

$$\begin{aligned}
D' &= EDoR_{SE} - EDoR_{SC} \\
&= \frac{1}{N_E} (n_{E1} \cdot EDoR_{E1} + \dots + n_{Em} \cdot EDoR_{Em}) - \frac{1}{N_C} (n_{C1} \cdot EDoR_{C1} + \dots + n_{Cm} \cdot EDoR_{Cm}) \\
&= \frac{1}{N_E} (n_{E1} \cdot p_{E1} M_{E1} + \dots + n_{Em} \cdot p_{Em} M_{Em}) - \frac{1}{N_C} (n_{C1} \cdot p_{C1} M_{C1} + \dots + n_{Cm} \cdot p_{Cm} M_{Cm})
\end{aligned}$$

By substituting the MLE for p_{Ei} , p_{Ci} , M_{Ei} , and M_{Ci} into the equation, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{D}' &= \widehat{EDoR}_{SE} - \widehat{EDoR}_{SC} \\
&= \frac{1}{N_E} (n_{E1} \cdot \widehat{EDoR}_{E1} + \dots + n_{Em} \cdot \widehat{EDoR}_{Em}) - \frac{1}{N_C} (n_{C1} \cdot \widehat{EDoR}_{C1} + \dots + n_{Cm} \cdot \widehat{EDoR}_{Cm})
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming response rate and DoR are independent, $\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{Ei})$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{Ei}) &= \text{Var}(\hat{p}_{Ei} \hat{M}_{Ei}) = E(\hat{p}_{Ei}^2 \hat{M}_{Ei}^2) - E(\hat{p}_{Ei} \hat{M}_{Ei})^2 = E(\hat{p}_{Ei}^2) E(\hat{M}_{Ei}^2) - E(\hat{p}_{Ei})^2 E(\hat{M}_{Ei})^2 \\
&= (\text{Var}(\hat{p}_{Ei}) + E(\hat{p}_{Ei})^2) (\text{Var}(\hat{M}_{Ei}) + E(\hat{M}_{Ei})^2) - E(\hat{p}_{Ei})^2 E(\hat{M}_{Ei})^2
\end{aligned}$$

$\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{Ci})$ is calculated similarly to $\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{Ei})$.

Then one can calculate the variance $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{D}')$ as the following:

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{D}') = \widehat{\text{Var}}(\widehat{EDoR}_{SE}) + \widehat{\text{Var}}(\widehat{EDoR}_{SC})$$

where $\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{SE})$ is calculated by summing over stratas, and $\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{SC})$ is calculated similarly to $\text{Var}(\widehat{EDoR}_{SE})$.

Therefore, the hypothesis that the EDoRs of the new drug E and the control drug C are equal can be tested as follows:

$$H_0: D' = 0 \text{ vs. } H_1: D' \neq 0$$

Using Z as the test statistic

$$Z = \frac{\hat{D}'}{\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{D}')}}}$$

Follows standard normal distribution under the null.

2.3 Parameter Estimation

Regarding the derivation of \hat{p}_i mentioned above, let m be the number of strata, p_i be the response rate of the i-th strata ($i = 1, \dots, m$), n_i be the number of patients in the i-th strata, where $i = 1, \dots, m$, and $X_{i,j}$ be the response indicator of the j-th patient in the i-th strata ($i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n_i$), indicating if the j-th patient in the i-th strata has responded to the treatment. The derivation of \hat{p}_i is as follows:

$$\parallel \begin{cases} X_{1,1}, X_{1,2}, \dots, X_{1,n_1} \\ X_{2,1}, X_{2,2}, \dots, X_{2,n_2} \\ \vdots \\ X_{m,1}, X_{m,2}, \dots, X_{m,n_m} \end{cases} \begin{matrix} \text{iid} \\ \text{iid} \\ \\ \text{iid} \end{matrix} \sim \begin{matrix} \text{Ber}(p_1) \\ \text{Ber}(p_2) \\ \\ \text{Ber}(p_m) \end{matrix} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \hat{p}_1 = \bar{X}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} X_{1,j} \\ \hat{p}_2 = \bar{X}_2 = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} X_{2,j} \\ \vdots \\ \hat{p}_m = \bar{X}_m = \frac{1}{n_m} \sum_{j=1}^{n_m} X_{m,j} \end{cases}$$

where $\hat{p}_1, \hat{p}_2, \dots, \hat{p}_m$ are the MLEs of p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m respectively. The formula for $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}_i)$ is as follows:

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{p}_i) = \frac{\hat{p}_i(1 - \hat{p}_i)}{n_i}$$

where $i = 1, \dots, m$.

As Ellis' method is a parametric framework, we similarly employed the accelerated failure time (AFT) model to estimate the DoR, since AFT is the most widely used parametric survival model. One can directly calculate its expected value and derive the formula for EDoR for patients with a response using AFT model.

We use the following parameterization of AFT model,

$$\log T_{ij} = \beta_0 + x_{ij}\beta_1 + \sigma\varepsilon_{ij}$$

In this paper, the distributions of T_{ij} are determined by the choice of ε_{ij} . We provided two choices for ε_{ij} : Case 1: standard normal distribution, which results in T_{ij} following a log normal distribution and Case 2: Gumbel (0,1) distribution, which results in T_{ij} following a Weibull distribution.

Let $\beta = (\beta_0, \beta_1)$ be the intercept and treatment effect, where x_{ij} is a dummy variable indicating treatment arm or control arm. In a two-arm randomized clinical trial, $x_{ij} = 1$ represents the experimental group for patient j in i -th strata, while $x_{ij} = 0$ represents the control group.

The derivations of the estimated EDoR \hat{M}_i are as follows:

Case 1: $\varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0,1)$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{ij} &\sim \log N(\beta_0 + x_{ij}\beta_1, \sigma^2) \\ E(T_{ij}) &= \exp\left(\beta_0 + x_{ij}\beta_1 + \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) \\ \hat{M}_i = \hat{E}(T_{ij}) &= \exp\left(\hat{\beta}_0 + x_{ij}\hat{\beta}_1 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

The $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{M}_i)$ can be derived using the delta method as follows:

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{M}_i) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_0} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_1} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\sigma}} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) \end{pmatrix}^T \begin{pmatrix} \text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_0) & \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\beta}_1) & \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\sigma}) \\ \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\beta}_1) & \text{Var}(\hat{\beta}_1) & \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_1, \hat{\sigma}) \\ \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_0, \hat{\sigma}) & \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_1, \hat{\sigma}) & \text{Var}(\hat{\sigma}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_0} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_1} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\sigma}} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
< \text{case 1} > x_{ij} = 0 & < \text{case 2} > x_{ij} = 1 \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_0} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp\left(\hat{\beta}_0 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2}\right) & \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_0} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp\left(\hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2}\right) \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_1} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_1} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp\left(\hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2}\right) \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\sigma}} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \hat{\sigma} \exp\left(\hat{\beta}_0 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2}\right) & \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\sigma}} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \hat{\sigma} \exp\left(\hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 + \frac{\hat{\sigma}^2}{2}\right)
\end{array}$$

Case 2: $\varepsilon_{ij} \sim \text{Gumbel}(0,1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{ij} &\sim \text{Weibull}\left(\exp(\beta_0 + x_{ij}\beta_1), \frac{1}{\sigma}\right) \\
E(T_{ij}) &= \exp(\beta_0 + x_{ij}\beta_1)\Gamma(1 + \sigma) \\
\hat{M}_i = \hat{E}(T_{ij}) &= \exp(\hat{\beta}_0 + x_{ij}\hat{\beta}_1)\Gamma(1 + \hat{\sigma})
\end{aligned}$$

where EDoR can be estimated by substituting the estimated MLE parameters and \hat{M}_i is an estimate of the mean duration of response in responding patients. We repeat the same process to derive $\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{M}_i)$:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
< \text{case 1} > x_{ij} = 0 & < \text{case 2} > x_{ij} = 1 \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_0} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp(\hat{\beta}_0)\Gamma(1 + \hat{\sigma}) & \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_0} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp(\hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1)\Gamma(1 + \hat{\sigma}) \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_1} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\beta}_1} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp(\hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1)\Gamma(1 + \hat{\sigma}) \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\sigma}} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp(\hat{\beta}_0)\Gamma(\hat{\sigma})(\hat{\sigma}\psi(\hat{\sigma}) + 1) & \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\sigma}} \hat{E}(T_{ij}) = \exp(\hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1)\Gamma(\hat{\sigma})(\hat{\sigma}\psi(\hat{\sigma}) + 1),
\end{array}$$

where $\psi(\cdot)$ is the digamma function. The details of the Weibull AFT model can be found in Liu (2023) et al.

After all parameters are estimated, \hat{p} , $\text{Var}(\hat{p})$, \hat{M} and $\text{Var}(\hat{M})$ can be combined into the D' and $\text{Var}(D')$ formulas and Z statistics for the stratified hypothesis test.

3. Simulation Study

In our extensive simulations, we compare our proposed difference test statistic (both stratified version and unstratified version) with the one introduced by Ellis et al. (2008), i.e., unstratified version of ratio test statistic. We allocate patients into four strata and divide them into experimental and control groups. We generate DoR data using an AFT model with both lognormal distribution and Weibull distribution. We investigate the empirical performance of our proposed test and unstratified test utilizing simulated data.

3.1 Simulation Setup

In the data generating process of simulation, we assume that DoR follows the log-normal and Weibull distributions from AFT model described in previous section, where T_{ij} is the DoR for the j-th patient in the i-th strata.

The data generation and parameter estimation are performed by using the Survival package in R. We generated 10000 datasets for each parameter setting and each dataset contains 500 patients and one stratification variable with 4 levels.

This study encompasses various scenarios, with each scenario being simulated 10000 times, recording the proportion of rejecting the null hypothesis at a two-sided type I error rate (α) of 0.05. By setting response rates $p_E = p_C$ being equal across strata, we investigate the case of expected duration of response in treatment arm greater than that of control by specifying β_1 greater than zero. When β_1 equals the zero, we are investigating under the null of no difference in expected duration of response. We considered different values of β_1 , and σ , and for simplicity, we simulated 25% censoring.

3.1 Simulation Results

From the following two tables, one can observe same trend regardless of which distribution T_{ij} is following. When β_1 's are all zeros across stratas, all tests are around 5%. When $\beta_1 = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$, the rejection rate for the stratified difference test is all higher than the rejection rate in the two unstratified test (both difference and ratio) for both $\sigma = 0.1$ and 0.3.

Table 1: The Simulation Results of Lognormal Distribution ($p_C = p_E = (0.6, 0.6, 0.6, 0.6)$, $\sigma = 0.1, 0.3$)

σ	β_1 's across stratas	Reject rate (Diff stratified)	Reject rate (Diff unstratified)	Reject rate (Ratio unstratified)
0.1	(0,0,0,0)	0.047	0.046	0.044
	(0.1,0,0,0)	0.078	0.072	0.070
	(0.1,0.1,0,0)	0.124	0.114	0.113
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0)	0.211	0.199	0.200
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0.1)	0.337	0.331	0.332
	(0.2,0,0,0)	0.102	0.076	0.076
	(0.2,0.2,0,0)	0.343	0.263	0.264
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0)	0.653	0.602	0.606
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2)	0.839	0.836	0.840
	(0.3,0,0,0)	0.139	0.087	0.087
	(0.3,0.3,0,0)	0.649	0.466	0.468
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0)	0.934	0.907	0.909
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0.3)	0.992	0.991	0.992
	(0.4,0,0,0)	0.022	0.122	0.121
(0.4,0.4,0,0)	0.584	0.635	0.637	

	(0.4,0.4,0.4,0)	0.994	0.992	0.993
	(0.4,0.4,0.4,0.4)	1.000	1.000	1.000
0.3	(0,0,0,0)	0.047	0.046	0.044
	(0.1,0,0,0)	0.078	0.072	0.070
	(0.1,0.1,0,0)	0.124	0.114	0.113
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0)	0.211	0.199	0.200
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0.1)	0.337	0.331	0.332
	(0.2,0,0,0)	0.102	0.076	0.076
	(0.2,0.2,0,0)	0.343	0.263	0.264
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0)	0.653	0.602	0.606
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2)	0.839	0.836	0.840
	(0.3,0,0,0)	0.139	0.087	0.087
	(0.3,0.3,0,0)	0.649	0.466	0.468
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0)	0.934	0.907	0.909
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0.3)	0.992	0.991	0.992
	(0.4,0,0,0)	0.122	0.122	0.121
	(0.4,0.4,0,0)	0.584	0.635	0.637
	(0.4,0.4,0.4,0)	0.994	0.992	0.993
(0.4,0.4,0.4,0.4)	1.000	1.000	1.000	

Table 2: The Simulation Results of Weibull Distribution ($p_C = p_E = (0.6,0.6,0.6,0.6)$, $\sigma = 0.1,0.3$)

σ	β_1 's across stratas	Reject rate (Diff stratified)	Reject rate (Diff unstratified)	Reject rate (Ratio unstratified)
0.1	(0,0,0,0)	0.045	0.044	0.042
	(0.1,0,0,0)	0.072	0.070	0.067
	(0.1,0.1,0,0)	0.134	0.126	0.124
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0)	0.199	0.195	0.194
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0.1)	0.320	0.315	0.316
	(0.2,0,0,0)	0.124	0.082	0.079

	(0.2,0.2,0,0)	0.307	0.266	0.269
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0)	0.585	0.585	0.586
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2)	0.812	0.809	0.812
	(0.3,0,0,0)	0.208	0.109	0.109
	(0.3,0.3,0,0)	0.619	0.486	0.491
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0)	0.920	0.952	0.954
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0.3)	0.988	0.988	0.989
	(0.4,0,0,0)	0.234	0.127	0.126
	(0.4,0.4,0,0)	0.782	0.669	0.671
	(0.4,0.4,0.4,0)	0.991	0.998	0.998
	(0.4,0.4,0.4,0.4)	1.000	1.000	1.000
0.3	(0,0,0,0)	0.046	0.047	0.046
	(0.1,0,0,0)	0.079	0.082	0.081
	(0.1,0.1,0,0)	0.099	0.091	0.091
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0)	0.160	0.160	0.160
	(0.1,0.1,0.1,0.1)	0.252	0.243	0.245
	(0.2,0,0,0)	0.116	0.102	0.102
	(0.2,0.2,0,0)	0.275	0.253	0.258
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0)	0.490	0.472	0.477
	(0.2,0.2,0.2,0.2)	0.728	0.725	0.730
	(0.3,0,0,0)	0.199	0.159	0.159
	(0.3,0.3,0,0)	0.556	0.504	0.507
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0)	0.822	0.805	0.812
	(0.3,0.3,0.3,0.3)	0.975	0.975	0.979
	(0.4,0,0,0)	0.288	0.201	0.202
	(0.4,0.4,0,0)	0.796	0.712	0.718
	(0.4,0.4,0.4,0)	0.977	0.969	0.972
(0.4,0.4,0.4,0.4)	1.000	1.000	1.000	

Figure 1: Power curve based on lognormal distribution ($\sigma = 0.3$) when there are $2\beta_1$'s not equal zero in 4 strata.

Figure 2: Power curve based on Weibull distribution ($\sigma = 0.3$) when there are $2\beta_1$'s not equal zero in 4 strata.

The two figures have demonstrated improved power in the stratified method over the non-stratified method under scenarios with $(\beta_1, \beta_1, 0, 0)$ for values of β_1 ranging from 0 to 0.6 where $\sigma = 0.3$.

From these two plots, our method consistently exhibits a higher power, regardless of whether the distribution is Weibull or lognormal, which shows the meaningfulness of our proposed methodology.

By observing the rate of rejecting the null hypothesis under different parameter combinations, we show improved performance of our stratified difference test statistics over unstratified version under the scenario of a stratified design.

4. Example: Acute Myelogenous Leukemia

In this section, the dataset used in this study was obtained from the survival package in R, which contains pseudo-realistic data on patients with acute myeloid leukemia from a real clinical trial derived from the data used by Le-Rademacher et al. (2018) and consists of 646 observations.

Like Ellis et al. (2008), there are 474 observations. The control group consists of 219 patients, and the experimental group has the remaining 255 patients with gender being stratification variable and around 25% censoring rate.

We employed the AFT model assuming random errors $\varepsilon_{ij} \sim \text{Gumbel}(0,1)$ and hence DoR_{ij} is following Weibull distribution, which is widely used in practice. The model framework is as follows:

$$\log DoR_{ij} = \beta_0 + x_{ij}\beta_1 + \sigma\varepsilon_{ij}$$

We considered the treatment group as the only covariate (dummy variable indicating treatment or control) and estimated the parameters and their covariance matrix using the survival package in R software.

We determined whether different treatment methods have significant differences by applying three distinct testing methods to two groups. The statistic calculated through stratified testing is 2.963, with a p-value of 0.0030. Meanwhile, for the two non-stratified methods, the statistics are 2.774 and 2.791, with p-values of 0.0052 and 0.0055, respectively.

Table 3: Analysis Results

	Diff stratified	Diff unstratified	Ratio unstratified
z-value	2.963	2.774	2.791
p-value	0.0030	0.0055	0.0052

Since all three p-values are less than 0.05, one can conclude that there is a significant difference in the treatment effect between the experimental group and the control group, with the experimental group exhibiting better treatment efficacy. Furthermore, it can be observed from these three p-values that the stratified testing provides stronger evidence than non-stratified testing for the presence of differential treatment effects between the two groups.

Discussion

The purpose of this paper is to propose a stratified difference test statistic for comparing the treatment effects between the experimental and control groups in a stratified design. We utilized the parametric AFT model for parameter estimation for duration of response and compared stratified and non-stratified testing methods through simulation results. Based on simulation results, when patients come from different strata, using a stratified hypothesis testing approach yields higher statistical power compared to not utilizing stratification information. Finally, we conducted an analysis using data from acute myeloid leukemia as an illustrative example.

One limitation of this research is that it assumes independence between response rate and duration of response like Ellis' method, hence incorporation of correlation between response rate and duration of response could be an interesting research area. Lastly, this paper uses parametric models to compare duration of response and non-parametric approaches using quantile regression could be further explored to relax model assumptions.

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